

Dear Sir / Madam,

The aim of this questionnaire is to find out and understand your opinions and perceptions of climate change when undertaking travel decisions as tourists and as citizens. This study is part of a large research project funded by the European Commission on the impacts of climate change on islands across Europe and the Caribbean. Your participation is anonymous, and the information shall be used exclusively for the purposes of the research undertaken. Please take your time and read the questions carefully. Thank you very much for your time and cooperation.

1.- Is it the first time you visit this island? 1. Yes 2. No, this is my _____ time in this island

2.- How many nights are you staying in this island? _____ nights

3.- Specify your type of accommodation:

1. Hotel	4. Family / Friends' House
2. Apartment / Bungalow	5. Hostel
3. Rural Accommodation	6. Other: _____

4.- On this occasion, which of the following options best describes the group you are travelling with?

1. Alone	4. With other relatives
2. With my partner	5. With your friends / work mates
3. With my children	6. Others: _____

5.- How many people came to the trip (also count yourself)? _____ people

6.- How did you organize the trip?

1. Organized it myself
2. Travel agency/tour operator
3. Other: _____

7.- How did you know about the destination? (It is possible to specify more than one option)

1. Internet	4. Had visited the island before
2. Advertisement on TV/radio/newspapers	5. Travel agency/ Tour operator
3. Friends and relatives	6. Other: _____

8.- Approximately, how much money have you spent on your trip to this island on average (PER PERSON)?

Flight / Transport to the island	_____ €
Accommodation	_____ €
Transport (in the island)	_____ €
Food and drinks	_____ €
Tours/ excursions	_____ €
Other expenses: _____	
Total	_____ €

9.- From a general point of view, on a scale from 1 to 7, how positive or negative is the image you have of this island?

Please, note that 1 indicates very negative and 7 very positive.

Very negative image	1 2 3 4 5 6 7	Very positive image
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10.- The following table indicates a series of opposing adjectives that can describe your opinion about this island.

Please, indicate on a scale from 1 to 7 to what degree your opinion of the island is closer to the adjective on the right or on the left.

Unpleasant destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Pleasant destination
Boring destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Inspiring destination
Sad destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Cheerful destination
Distressing destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Relaxing destination

11.- How would you rate the state of conservation of the natural environment of this island in general, based on your knowledge and information?

Please, consider that: 1=very badly preserved; 7=very well preserved.

State of conservation of the natural environment						
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

12.- For the following environmental attributes, how would you rate their importance for your travelling decisions in general?

Please, consider that: 1=not important at all; 7=very important.

Attribute	Importance						
Comfortable air temperature	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Comfortable water temperature	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Lack of infectious diseases	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Beach size	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Water availability	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Lack of wildfires	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Well preserved marine wildlife	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Well preserved land flora and fauna	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Landscape	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Well preserved infrastructures and facilities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Cultural heritage	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Scarce rainfall	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Lack of extreme weather events	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Let me briefly inform you about Climate Change:

Climate change is a global phenomenon created predominantly by burning fossil fuels (petrol, carbon, gas ...), which adds heat-trapping gases to Earth's atmosphere. Consequences include increased temperature, sea level rise, ice mass loss in the Earth's Poles, shifts in flower/plant blooming, and extreme weather events.

Below you can find a description of the major potential impacts of climate change in European Islands, such as the one we are now.

In this study we are interested in knowing how you would value SOME POLICIES that would combat these climate change impacts in this island. Consider that THESE POLICIES are going to be implemented by the local authorities, and there is the need to know how valuable they are to you as tourists.

Please, read carefully the description of potential impacts of climate change and the POLICIES that can be undertaken for each of the impacts of climate change in this island.

IMPACT

POLICY

Thermal Comfort: Climate Change increases the frequency and severity of heat waves, which are periods of several days or weeks of excessive hot weather, including warmer nights and hotter days.

HEAT WAVES AMELIORATION: This policy consists of early warning, proper information for vulnerable groups, air conditioning in public indoor and outdoor places, increasing green and watered areas and provision of proper medical care for heat-related diseases.

Without Policy

With Policy

Infectious Diseases: Climate change is likely to increase the occurrence of infectious diseases such as malaria and dengue, which are transported by some species of mosquitos that manage to survive under the new climatic conditions.

INFECTIOUS DISEASES PREVENTION: This policy consists of proper information and advisement to face outbreaks, fumigation of mosquitoes' prone areas, and emergency medical care plans.

Without Policy

With Policy

Beaches Availability: Climate change may cause sandy beaches disappear because of sea level rise and the increase of storms.

BEACHES PROTECTION: This involves building seawalls and breakwaters, nourishment of sandy beaches when needed and building compensatory artificial beaches across coastal areas.

Without Policy

With Policy

IMPACT

POLICY

Water Availability: Climate change is reducing the water availability. Many areas around the world will present water shortages and scarcity, facing droughts.

WATER SUPPLY: This includes desalination plants and water facilities reinforcement to guarantee fresh water supply.

Without Policy

With Policy

Forest Fires: Climate change is increasing the number and effects of forest fires fuelled by warmer climatic conditions and droughts.

FOREST FIRES PREVENTION: This policy consists of improving forest management to reduce combustibility, increasing firefighting technical and human resources, and investing more in post-fires landscape and habitats restoration.

Without Policy

With Policy

13. – How would you CHANGE your travelling decisions if the following impacts occur AT THIS ISLAND?

Please, consider the following answers: 1=Definitely, I would NOT change destination; 2=I would choose different dates, but same destination; 3=Most likely, I would NOT change destination; 4=Most likely, I would change destination; 5=Definitely, I would change destination.

Climate Change Impact	Would you CHANGE destination?				
	No	No, but I'd change date	Probably No	Probably Yes	Yes
Infectious diseases become more widespread	1	2	3	4	5
Streets are frequently flooded as a result of rain or tidal surge	1	2	3	4	5
Beaches largely disappear	1	2	3	4	5
Storms intensify throughout the year	1	2	3	4	5
Temperature becomes uncomfortably hot to me	1	2	3	4	5
Rainfall daily duration becomes uncomfortable to me	1	2	3	4	5
Wind strength becomes uncomfortable to me	1	2	3	4	5
Marine wildlife largely disappears	1	2	3	4	5
Corals severely bleach	1	2	3	4	5
Beaches are affected by algae blooms	1	2	3	4	5
Wildfires occur more often	1	2	3	4	5
Coastal infrastructures are damaged due to coastal erosion	1	2	3	4	5
Terrestrial wildlife largely disappears	1	2	3	4	5
Temperature becomes uncomfortably cold to me	1	2	3	4	5
Cultural heritage is damaged due to weather conditions	1	2	3	4	5
Water is scarce for leisure activities	1	2	3	4	5

14.- Now, you are going to be presented with various combinations of the aforementioned climate change POLICIES to be undertaken in this island that would counteract the impacts described, and you are asked to choose the one that you prefer.

For each option describing a set of climate change policies, you are asked to pay an extra price per person per day of your stay, above the current expenses that you have incurred in your vacation in this island.

For each model, please choose your preferred option (ONLY ONE) between the alternatives proposed.

Model A.1

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

3€

5€

0€

Mark your choice

Model A.2

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

7€

1€

0€

Mark your choice

Model A.3

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

3€

5€

0€

Mark your choice

Model A.4

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

3€

5€

0€

Mark your choice

Model A.5

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

5€

3€

0€

Mark your choice

Model A.6

Option A

Option B

Neither Option

Heat Waves Amelioration

Infectious Diseases Prevention

Beaches Protection

Water Supply

Forest Fires Prevention

NO POLICY

Price (per day per person)

1€

7€

0€

Mark your choice

OTHER INFORMATION

15.- Country of Residence: _____ Province: _____

16.- Gender: 1. Male 2. Female 3. Other

17.- Age: _____

18.- Education level:

1. No schooling completed	4. Technical/vocational training
2. Primary school	5. Bachelor's degree
3. Secondary school	6. Master or Doctorate degree

19.- Employment status:

1. Unemployed	4. Employee
2. Student	5. Retired
3. Self-employed	6. Other: _____

20.- How many people live in your household (also count yourself)? _____

21.- Net monthly income:

Individual	
<500€	2001-2800€
500-1200€	2801-3500€
1201-2000€	>3501€

Household (total)	
<500€	2201-3000€
500-1500€	3001-4000€
1501-2200€	>4001€

THANK YOU very much for your participation!

To be completed by the interviewer:	Interview #: _____
Name of the island: _____	Date: ____/____/20____
Location of the interview: _____	Time: _____:_____
Duration of the interview: _____ min	Interviewer: _____